

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Development of a rapid LC method for Metopimazine based on a Quality by Design (QbD) approach

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 09 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

ethnobotanical use,
pharmacological profile,
medicinal plant,
phytochemicals.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14327605

ABSTRACT

laxative, antipyretic expectorant and treatment for malarial infection and infantile diarrhoea. The plant is extensively found in tropical and subtropical regions globally with several phytochemicals including terpenoids, flavonoids, sterols and cardenolides, extracted and identified from its different parts (leave, shoot, root, seeds and fruits). Pergularia daemia is extensively utilised by the treatment of disease like cancer, ulcers, diabetes, tuberculosis, diuretics, helminthetics. The plant's root has been primarily utilised to cure jaundice and liver illness. The current review article focuses on the chemical component, therapeutic quality and other significant elements.

INTRODUCTION

OVERVIEW Plants and plant-derived products have long been utilised as a source of medication. The World Health Organisation (WHO) reports that traditional plant-based medicines serve as the primary source of healthcare for over 80% of the world's population, the majority of whom live in developing and impoverished nations [1]. Researchers studying medicinal plants are becoming more prevalent in the pharmaceutical industry due to the effectiveness and safety of herbal medication. There is strong evidence of a rise in demand for medicinal plants as a result of

the global trend towards a higher "quality of life" [2]. The use of plants to cure a variety of human and animal ailments is as old as humanity. India possesses an abundant array of medicinally valuable plants. There are many uses for these plants in pharmaceutical preparations in modern medicine. [3]. India has about 25,000 medicinal formulations based on herbs, mostly utilised in traditional and folk medicine [4]. These medication formulations come from specific plant parts such as leaves, roots, stems, bark, flowers, and seeds, or they come directly from the aerial

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

portion of the plant. Certain herbal medications are derived from plant excretory materials like latex and resins. [5]. There is a very restricted supply of bioactive phytochemicals because not all plant kinds can yield them. Medicinal plants that are employed in Ayurvedic and Siddha medicine are less poisonous and retain physiologically active structures that aid in the creation of complementary therapies [6]. The demand for therapeutic plants and herbal extracts is rising steadily in Europe and other developed nations. India is a prominent supplier of medical plant extracts with added value and herbs (Export of Herbs and Herbal Products, 2019). Several therapeutic plants and their extracts are used in herbal medicine, which is a subset of alternative medicine. The safest and most efficient way to treat patients is with this kind of care (Source: herbal medicine). University of Maryland Medical Centre). Herbal remedies are made directly from a variety of plant materials, including leaves, stem bark, roots, bark, flowers, and seeds. The majority of herbal compositions in the Ayurvedic system were made using polyherbal formulas. Also, they exhibited a considerable benefit against various chronic disorders. The terms powers (Churna), decoction (Kwatha), resins (Guggul), oil (Taila), infusion (Phanta), etc., refer to the various herbal preparations [7]. *Pergularia* (Forsk.) *Chiov* (Apocyanaceae), sometimes called *dustapuchettu* (Telugu), *uttamarani* (Sanskrit), or *utaran* in Hindi, is a thin, laticiferous plant that grows on the plains across hot regions of India. It has a foetid fragrance. Because *P. Daemia* has a wide spectrum of therapeutic capabilities for a variety of ailments, it is thought to have more magical than medicinal applications. This plant is used by some Folklore people as a laxative, an expectorant, an antipyretic, and a treatment for jaundice in infants. In Ghana, the sap extracted from the leaves is believed to treat irritated eyes, while the latex from the leaves is used as a topical analgesic. The herb lowers the

frequency of asthma attacks and seizures. The menstrual cycle is regulated by gastrointestinal processes. [8]. The root can be used to cure piles, leprosy, mental illnesses, and anaemia. The folkloric people of Salem, Dharmapuri, and Coimbatore district, Tamilnadu state, India, have long employed the roots of *Pergularia daemia* to heal pain, inflammation, and fever. The southern regions of India are home to both plants in large numbers. *P. daemia* (Asclepiadaceae) is called as "Veliparuthi." [9] *Pergularia daemia* The Asclepiadaceae family includes *forsk.* It is a perennial twining herb seen growing untamed by India's roadside. *P. Daemia*'s aerial parts are utilised as an antibacterial, antihelminthic, and antivenomous agent. Additionally, it is used to treat menstrual, uterine, and stomach ulcers. However, the plant's leaves are also a useful remedy for a number of medical conditions, including whooping cough, asthma, bronchitis, anaemia, leprosy, arthritis, haemorrhoids, amenorrhoea, dysmenorrhoea, infantile diarrhoea, and bodily discomfort [10]. According to recent findings, the pharmacological effect of *P. Daemia*'s aerial parts has been shown to prevent a number of illnesses. In the current review, we discuss the current state of *P. Daemia*'s phytochemistry and pharmacological activity based on this background investigation.

PLANT REVIEW

General information:-

[11] a thin, hispid, foul-smelling, evergreen climber. Petioles are 2–9 cm long, petioles are opposite, membranous, broadly ovate, orbicular or deeply cordate, sharp or short-acuminate at apex, hairy beneath, and leaves are 3–9 cm long and roughly as wide. Flowers are borne in axillary, long-peduncled, drooping clusters and are greenish-yellow or dull white with a purple tinge. Follicles (fruits) are lanceolate, broadly ovate, long-pointed, and approximately 5 cm long. They are covered in soft spines. In central India, flowers

may bloom from August to January every year, while fruits will ripen from October to February. The stems in the deciduous woods of central India usually die down in February and then regrow when green the rainy season begins.

fig.(1)Fruits of perguleria deamia

fig.(2) Flower of perguleria deamia

fig.(3) Leaves of peruguleria

fig.(4) Root of perguleria deamia

BOTANICAL DISTRIBUTION:-

Tropical and subtropical locations, especially India, Africa, Arabia, Malaya, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and some areas of south-east Asia, are home to a large population of Pergularia. The majority of the time, it is found in India's hedgerows, growing to an altitude of roughly 1000 meters in the Himalaya and 900 meters in the southern regions.

Fig-Distribution of p deamia in Africa and Asia

[12] Common and local names:-
 P.daemia (Forsk) Chiv or P.extensa N.E.Br or Daemia
 Extensa R.Br 15
 Bengali: Chagulbanti , Changulbati
 Gujarati: Amaradudheli, Chamardudhel
 Hindi: Utranajutuka, Utran, Dudhi, Dudhibel
 Kannada : Haalu koratige, Hala koratige
 Malayalam : Veliparatti, Veliparuti
 Marathi : Utranavel, U
 Ethnomedical Informed Mellitus17. Entire plant used as an anthelmintic, Emmenagogue, emetic, antiseptic, emetic , expectorant18-20
 Oriya : Juktiruhi, Uttruri, Uturdi
 Sanskrit : Uttaravaruni, Kurutakah, Yugaphala,
 Tamil : Beliparti, Nandamani, Uthamani, Veliparuth
 [13] Species:-
 1] perguleria adenophylla schltr and k.schum-cameron
 2] perguleria brunoniana (wight and Arn) D.dietr India
 3] perguleria Salesian (wight) bunch- hum
 4] perguleria clausa (R.br) spreng jamaica
 5] perguleria Exilis (forks) chiov-Africa,s Asia
 6] perguleria flavescens (colebr) spreng-bangladesh
 7] perguleria Hamilton ii (wight) D.dietr Uttar Pradesh
 8] perguleria rostrata- (RBr) spreng Queensland
 9] perguleria raylei (wight) D dietr.himachal Pradesh
 10] perguleria raylei (weight) spreng.Australia
 [14]Scientific classification :-
 Kingdom: plantae

Subkingdom : Tracheobionta
 Super division: Spermatophyta
 Division : Magnoliophyta
 Class : Magnoliopsida
 Subclass : Asteridae
 Order : Gentianales
 Family : Asclepiadaceae
 Genus : Pergularia
 Ethnomedical Data:- Aerial sections and entirety
 A plant called Dibetis Mellitus(15) is used to treat snake bites. (16)Whole plant used as expectorant, emmenagogue, emetic, antiseptic, and anthelminticand antivenin, and used to aid in parturition21; in Ayurvedic medicine, it is used to treat postpartum haemorrhage as well as snakebite, amenorrhoea, asthma, and delayed childbirth. This plant’s latex is used to treat ulcers and boils .(17)
 Dried leaf is used as an emetic, an antirheumatic, and a treatment for bronchitis, amenorrhoea, dysmenorrhoea, asthma, wound healing, whooping cough, and to make childbirth easier. While leaf juice is used to cure amenorrhoea, dysmenorrhoea, catarrhal infections, infantile diarrhoea, and to alleviate bodily discomfort, entire leaves are used to treat dibetis mellitus. Fresh leaves are used as fish poison. (18) Fresh root used for constipation, cough, asthma, and bronchitis, and dried root used as an emetic and abortifacient (19).while fresh root used as an abortifacient and used to treat gonorrhea.shoots used to treat whooping cough steam bark use in treat malaria
 Phytochemicals in p.deamia :-
 Table1 and 2 :-Initial qualitative phytochemical screening of P. Daemia leaf and root extracts using various solvent extracts

Table.(1)

Phytochemicals	Leaf						
	AE	EE	ME	PEE	CE	ACE	EAE
Carbohydrate	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
Proteins & Amino acid	-	-	-	+	-	NA	-
Glycosides	+	+	NA	+	+	+	-
Alkaloids	-	-	+	-	+	+	NA

Steroids	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
Favonoids	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Saponins	+	+	NA	+	+	NA	-
Tannins	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
Fixed oils & Fats	-	+	-	+	+	NA	-
☐ Gums & Mucilage's	-	-	+	-	-	NA	-
Terpenoids	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
Coumarins	NA	+	N A	+	+	NA	-
Phytosterols	NA	+	+	+	+	NA	+
Phenols	+	+	+	-	+	N A	-

Table.(2)

Phytochemicals	ROOT					
	AE	EE	PEE	CE	EAE	
Carbohydrates	+	+	-	-	-	
Proteins & Amino acids	-	-	-	-	-	
Glycosides	+	+	-	-	-	
Alkaloids	+	-	-	+	-	
Steroids	+	+	-	+	+	
Favonoids	+	+	-	+	-	
Saponins	+	+	-	-	-	
Tannins	+	+	-	+	-	
Fixed oils & Fats	-	-	+	-	-	
Gums & Mucilage's	+	+	-	-	-	
Terpenoids	+	+	-	-	+	
Coumarins	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Phytosterols	NA	+	NA	NA	NA	
Phenols	+	+	-	+	-	

+ presence, - absence, NA not analyzed (AE Aqueous extract; EE Ethanol extract; ME Methanol extract; PEE Petroleum ether extract; CE Chloroform extract; ACE Acetone extract; EAE Ethyl acetate extract)

(20) Pharmaceuticals, dietary supplements, and merchandise. It is possible to extract phytochemicals from dried or fresh plant samples. When compared to dried powdered extraction, the freeze drying extraction process often preserves higher amounts of phenolic content in plant samples [21]. Since solvent extractions are so versatile, easy to use, and efficient, they are the method most frequently employed to prepare extracts from plant sources. Many techniques have lately been developed,

including supercritical extraction, solid-liquid extraction, Microwave extraction, Conventional Extraction and Ultrasound Extraction etc. [22]. Currently, this is one of the most widely and commonly used combination of techniques for separation, identification and quantification of polyphenolic Compounds [23]. The primary applications of mass spectrometry (MS) include the quantitative and qualitative study of biological substances. The gas phase ions that are separated according to their mass-to-charge ratios (m/z) form the basis of this technique. Mass spectrometry (MS) is a widely used and effective method for determining the mass and elucidating the structure of biomolecules [24]. The most used analytical method for the majority of tasks,

including plant metabolite analysis and drug development, is HPLC combined with MS. Different chemical components can be found in the whole plant, leaves, stem, and root extract of *Perguleria* D.. B-sitosterol, lupeol, oleanolic acid, calactin, calotropin, corotoxigenin, daucosterol, sucrose, α -amyrin, β -amyrin, and its acetate are present in *P. Daemia* leaf and root extract. The complete plant extract also contained phytochemicals that were identified, including betaine, hentriacontane, pentacosanoic acid, polypeptide, and glucoside of *Daemia extensa* (synonymous *Perguleria daemia*). [25]. Phytochemicals including calactin, calotropin, calotropigenin, corotoxigenin, dihydrocalotropigenin, protoscharin, uscharidin, and uscharin are present in *Perguleria daemia* seed extract. In a similar vein, Mittal et al. [26] discovered many cardenolides in seed extract, including uscharidin and calotoxin. Upon qualitative analysis, flavonoids were determined to be the primary and significant phytochemicals extracted from the aerial section of *Perguleria daemia*. *Perguleria daemia*'s vegetative portions were found to contain hyperoside (flavonol), whereas the fresh shoots and flowers were found to have flavonoids and saponins. [27]. The presence of flavonoids, such as flavones, isoflavones, flavonoidoids, anthocyanin, coumarin lignans, catechins, and isocatechins, is particularly responsible for the antioxidant activity of the plants [28]. Flavonoids and phenolic acids are two examples of polyphenolic chemicals that are abundant in fresh fruit juices and green leafy vegetables. These herbal based anti-oxidant substances or medications protect diseases including atherosclerosis, stroke, diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, cancer, and other anti-inflammatory disorders. Crucially, previous papers have detailed the anti-inflammatory properties of phytochemical and some are currently undergoing preclinical testing

[1] B- amyrin

[2] A- amyrin

[3] Oleanolic acid acetate

[4] Lupeol acetate

[5] Daucosterol.

[6] B- sitosterol

A.phytocompound found in entire plant and root extract of perguleria daemia

[5] uscharidin.

[1] Calotropin.

[6] calotropagenin

B.cardenolides found in seed ,steam ,and entire plant extract perguleria demia

[2] calactin

[1] chyoeriol.

[3]calotroxin

[2] quercetin

[4] calotropin .

[3]formononetin.

[4] Naringenin.

[5] taxifolin.

C. Flavonoids found in the flower, leaf stem, and extract of the entire plant *Pergularia daemia*

[29] These flavonoids may block other inflammatory agents as well as pro-inflammatory mediators. [30] identified and reported that *P.*

Daemia extracts consist of five flavonoids (formononetin,

Quercetin, chrysoeriol, taxifolin and naringenin) which

Has anti-arthritic activity against complete Freund's adju-

vant (CFA) induced rat model. Flavonoids contain numerous health-promoting qualities, including important subclasses of flavonoids include flavanols, flavanones, isoflavones, flavones. Flavonoids have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, and immunomodulatory properties.

Pharmacological Profile:-

Regarding Phytomedicine: [31] *Pergularia daemia* is a plant that has long been used to treat malarial intermittent fevers, infantile diarrhoea, and diarrhoea. It is both a laxative and anthelmintic. It is extensively found throughout the world's tropical and subtropical climates. Different sections of the plant (leaves, stems, shoots, roots, seeds, and fruits) have yielded the isolation and

identification of numerous phytochemicals, such as terpenoid, flavonoids, sterols, and cardenolids. In the Western Ghats of India, *P. Daemia* is widely utilised by different tribal people to treat a wide range of illnesses; the plant's roots, on the other hand, are mostly used to treat jaundice and liver sickness. The current review article focusses on chemical components, therapeutic qualities, and other significant of *p.daemia* Anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity:- In order to shield the tissue from harm, inflammation is a normal biological process that reacts to external invaders, including bacteria. Normally, inflammation is a quick and self-limiting process, but in abnormal clinical conditions, it produces excessive ROS and RNS, which can result in a persistent state of inflammation. Prolonged inflammation has been associated with severe inflammatory conditions such as cancer, arthritis, neurological, metabolic, and cardiovascular disorders. but they also have a number of negative side effects. However, therapeutic plants with minimal side effects, such as *P. Daemia*, have curative results.

Anti arthritis activity:-

The phytochemicals in treating anti-rheumatic conditions in animal models [32] The study on the methanolic extract treated rat groups effectively reduced the paw inflammation and also significantly increased the levels of serum biochemical markers such as haemoglobin [33] There is also a suggestion that *P. Daemia*'s anti-rheumatic action may be attributed to phytochemicals like sterols and flavonoids.

Anti oxidant activity:-

Pergularia daemia root extract was subjected to an in vitro screening procedure for antioxidant activity. In their initial phytochemical test, For glucoside, steroids, flavonoids The findings of their investigation indicate that [34]. *P. Daemia* demonstrated antioxidant action, which may be explained by the presence of various

phytochemical ingredients and polyphenolic compounds.

Anti -cancer :-

The anticancer activity of Pergularia daemia was tested against sixty human cancer cell lines and arranged into sub panels that represented cancers of the lung, colon, kidney, ovary, and central nervous system. The results showed that α -amyrin had low potency anticancer activity. Triterpenoids are essential anti-cancer agents, and structural modification of this class of compounds can lead to the development of a novel medication for the treatment of cancer[35].

Anti-diabetes Activity:-

Pergularia daemia plant extract and ethanol were tested against alloxan-induced hyperglycemia; 200 mg kg⁻¹ of the extract significantly brought blood glucose levels back to normal, demonstrating hypoglycemic activity. [36]The hypoglycemic activity of P. Daemia extract may be attributed to the presence of quercetin and β -sitosterol. P. Daemia on blood glucose level status in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. The results indicated that oral administration of P. Daemia possesses significant antidiabetic potential. It was concluded that the plant's antidiabetic effect may be due to its bioactive compounds present in the leaves extract

Diuretics Activity:-

Examined the dose-dependent oral diuretic effect of P. Daemia extracts in rats.[37] The Lipschitz test was used in this investigation, and furosemide was the recommended drug. The results showed that the diuretic activity of the Pergularia daemia alcoholic extract peaked at 400 ml/kg concentration, with an activity of 0.93. When compared to the control urine production, all examined extracts showed significant results ($P < 0.001$), with the exception of petroleum ether.steroids, flavonoids, and alkaloids are a few examples of potential culprits for P. Daemia's diuretic action.

Anti-tuberculosis Activity:-

Global health organisation (WHO) data from 2017 states that 10.4 million cases of tuberculosis (TB) were recorded in 2016, with one significant potential reason for passing away. Plant extracts have been shown in the Ayurvedic medical system to have potential benefits in the treatment of tuberculosis. Lately, Mishra . [38]. ATD administration dramatically lowered the levels of albumin and glucose. In addition, elevated levels of bilirubin, triglycerides, cholesterol, alkaline phosphatase, aspartate aminotransferase, and bilirubin were detected. Following exposure to ATDs, they observed an increase in lipid peroxidation and a decrease in glutathione, superoxide dismutase, glutathione, peroxidase, and glutathione reductase catalase. Therefore, in comparison to the control, P. Daemia extract considerably preserved these serum biochemical parameters and antioxidant components.

Anti-fertility activity:-

A possible anti-fertility effect was demonstrated by the steroidal component of P. Daemia and its ethanolic extract. Significant efficacy was seen with a steroidal fraction of 200 mg/kg against female mice during the pre-implantation period. On the other hand, 600 mg/kg of ethanolic extracts showed late abortifacient action. The extract demonstrated 100% activity without any mortality after 48 hours of medication administration. [39]

Anthelmintic activity:-

According to Kumar et al. [40], P. Daemia's ethanolic extract has greater anthelmintic activity than its aqueous extract. Using albendazole as a reference medication, they tested the leaf extracts' effectiveness against Ascaris lumbricoides, Eudrillus eugeniae, and Taenia solium roundworms at a concentration of 100 mg/ml. For the round worm, the paralysis and the time of death were observed in an ethanolic extract. Extracts from P. Daemia caused paralysis and

death in worms, and at 100 mg/ml, they showed ($P < 0.01$) more anthelmintic activity than the conventional medication.

Anti-ulcer activity:-

In the process of ulcer development pathophysiology, dehydration, disruption of mucosal cellular membranes, and Ethanol directly imposed cytotoxic effects, which ultimately caused the inflammatory response to proliferate.[41].Meanwhile, leukocytes—which cause oxidative stress, apoptosis, and inflammatory responses—led alcohol to indirectly cause harmful effects. NF-kappa B (NF-κB) is a key mediator of the growing illness condition in this process.[42].The anti-ulcerogenic potential of second-ary metabolites such flavonoids, tannins, and triterpenes has been well documented [43].These phytochemicals found in Perguleria daemia may be the cause of its anti-ulcer properties. P. Daemia showed a healing effect on rats with ethanol-induced ulcers. The group that received normal medication treatment demonstrated 78.73% inhibition percentage, whereas extracts at 400 mg/kg showed 63.01 percent.

Antibacterial activity :- [45]. Perguleria daemia's ethanol extract showed antibacterial action. Additionally, a recent study demonstrated the antibacterial efficacy of leaf extract from Perguleria daemia against B. Subtilis, S. Aureus, E. Coli, and P. Vulgari using a variety of solvents, including hexane, chloroform, and ethyl .

CONCLUSION:-

One of the medicinal plants with the fewest studies and scientific reports is P. Daemia's we suggest that Perguleria daemia showed good pharmacological action based from the conventional reports and literature surveys One of the medicinal plants with the fewest studies and scientific reports is perguleria daemia's. We suggest that P. Daemia showed good pharmacological action based from the

conventional reports and literature surveys. Proteins, amino acids, terpenoids, flavonoids, phytosterols, and saponins have all been extracted and identified through qualitative analysis from various portions of P. Daemia. One well-known natural source of phytochemicals and bioactive substances is medicinal plants. In P. Daemia preparations, natural flavonoids and cardenolides are the main bioactive substances identified. Bioactive substances with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and other associated properties in humans that are implicated in pharmaceutical actions. When P. Dae-mia solvent extracts are administered, inflammation and a number of illnesses, including as cancer and arthritis, are avoided.

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HOW TO CITE: Pratiksha G. Pathade*, Afnanuddin K. Sayyed, Dr. Rajendra M. Kawade, Salunke Chaitali B., Development of a rapid LC method for Metopimazine based on a Quality by Design (QbD) approach, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 966-978. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327605>

